

Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with Mixed Ligand Schiff Bases Ψ

M. B. HALLI* and A. C. HIREMATH

Department of Chemistry, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga-585 106

Manuscript received 17 November 1995, revised 6 May 1996, accepted 19 June 1996

The mixed ligand complexes of metal ions have been extensively studied in recent years following the recognition that they play an important role in biological processes¹. Cyanopyridines with different aryl and alkyl groups have been found to possess various biological activities². In continuation of our work on Schiff base complexes, we report here the complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with mixed ligands derived from condensation of 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridine and substituted-salicylaldehydes or orthohydroxyacetophenone.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are lightly brown coloured shining amorphous solids and stable towards air. The elemental analyses show 1 : 1 : 1 (M : L : L') molar ratio, where M = Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}, L = 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridine and L' = substituted-salicylaldehyde or acetophenone. The observed low molar conductance values (9.50–15.00 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹) for the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes reveal their non-electrolytic nature. The Cu^{II} complexes are paramagnetic having magnetic moment values in the range 1.80–1.88 B.M. The nickel complexes are diamagnetic in nature.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Metal % : Found/ (Calcd.)	Mol. cond. Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹
Cu(C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O)	220	13.84 (13.97)	10.50
Cu(C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₄ OCl)	215	12.95 (13.01)	10.00
Cu(C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O)	230	13.02 (13.55)	11.30
Cu(C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O)	220	13.89 (13.55)	10.60
Ni(C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O)	210	13.41 (13.01)	15.5
Ni(C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₄ OCl)	220	12.59 (12.11)	10.25
Ni(C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O)	240	13.01 (12.93)	12.75
Ni(C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O)	225	12.84 (12.93)	9.45

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

The Cu^{II} mixed ligand complexes show a single broad band at 16 000–20 000 cm⁻¹ suggesting square-planar structure for Cu^{II} complexes³. The absence of any band below 10 000 cm⁻¹ rules out the possibility of tetrahedral geometry⁴. The electronic spectra of the divalent Ni^{II} complexes display single absorption band at 17 000–20 500 cm⁻¹, which resemble those of square-planar Ni^{II} complexes⁵. The high intensity band at 23 000–25 000 cm⁻¹ may be due to overlap of charge transfer band. The absence of any band in the region 10 000–15 000 cm⁻¹ is an evidence for the absence of an octahedral or tetrahedral structure.

The ir spectral study of the metal complexes gives informations about the nature of metal-ligand bond, molecular symmetry, electron distribution and stability of the complexes⁶. The three strong intensity bands at 3 450, 3 250 and 3 180 cm⁻¹ are attributed to NH stretching vibrations in 2-amino-3-cyano-4,5-disubstituted-pyridine. These bands shift to lower frequency on complexation by about 40–150 cm⁻¹ and in some cases became weak and broad. This shifting suggests the coordination through nitrogen atom of NH group in all the complexes. The strong intensity band appearing at 2 225 cm⁻¹ (C≡N) in 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridine disappears on complexation, indicating the coordination through the nitrogen of nitrile group⁷. The disappearance of the band may be due to decrease in the bond order of C≡N and increase in the bond order of C=N. The strong ligand band observed at 1 620–1 650 cm⁻¹ (aldehydic or ketonic C=O) however disappears and a new band at 1 590–1 610 cm⁻¹ appears in the complexes. This corresponds to C=N stretch and indicates the formation of Schiff base.

The non-ligand medium intensity bands are observed at 470–560 (M–O) and 410–465 cm⁻¹ (M–N) in all the complexes as per the earlier reports⁸.

Based on the above results a square-planar structure may be proposed for all the complexes.

Experimental

The 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridine was prepared by the literature method⁹.

Mixed ligand complexes : To a solution of metal chloride (0.1 mol) in alcohol (10 ml), a mixture of salicylaldehydes or *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.1 mol) and 2-amino-3-cyano-4,6-disubstituted-pyridine (0.1 mol) was

Ψ Abstract of the paper presented at 12 ICC, Conference held at Warangal, 1993.

NOTE

added in the same solvent and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 0.5 h. Dilute alcoholic ammonia solution was added to it and the contents were refluxed for 0.5 h, then cooled and the resulting complexes were washed with alcohol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 .

The magnetic, conductance and spectral measurements were followed as described elsewhere¹⁰.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to authorities of Gulbarga University, Gulbarga, for facilities.

References

1. L. HELLERMAN and C. C. STOCK, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1938 **125**, 771; B. G. NALMSTRON, *Arch. Biol. Chem. Bio. Phys.*, 1953, **58**, 398.
2. H. H. MOUSA, L. M. CHABAKA and P. ZAKI, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1983, **26**, 469; C. M. CARSON, R. J. EHR and R. B. ROGERS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **92**, 6537; J. J. BALDWIN, E. L. ENGELHARDT, R. HIRSCHMANN, G. S. PONTICELLO, J. G. ATKINSON, B. K. WASSON, C. S. SWEET and A. SCRIBINE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1980, **23**, 65; C. S. SWEET, A. SCRIBINE and C. A. STONE, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1979, **211**, 200.
3. L. SACCONI and M. GIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 276.
4. M. S. PATIL and J. R. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 79.
5. M. B. HALLI, N. V. HUGGI and A. C. HIREMATH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 374.
6. C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1963; K. NAKAMOTI, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Eastern, New Delhi, 1970.
7. M. M. MOSTAFA, S. M. HASSAN and A. F. A. E. I. ASNY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 529.
8. H. KUMA, K. MOCIBE, W. MORE and S. YAMADA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1980, **53**, 3214; A. C. FEBERTTI, G. C. GRANCHINI and G. PEYRONEL, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1980, **36**, 698.
9. L. PRAKASH, P. TANEJA and S. S. VERMAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **75**, 798.
10. A. C. HIREMATH, M. B. HALLI and N. V. HUGGI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 607